

Coding Summary by File

Beyond Open Research II

23/09/2025 11:37

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
----------------	-----------	----------	-----------------------------	------------------	-------------------	-------------

Dataset

Files\\Motivation for Public Involvement Exercise

Code

Codes\\Collaboration & communication

No	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
	0.1354	13			
communicating			1	JS	20/08/2025 14:52
Motivational – to keep researching when you see people’s enthusiasm			2	JS	20/08/2025 15:02
Get new ideas from the public			3	JS	20/08/2025 15:02
By involving public you develop knowledge about their need and how to reach them			4	JS	20/08/2025 15:03
Public meaningful involvement will shape somehow the researcher’s approach to the project			5	JS	20/08/2025 15:04
Cochrane collaboration collects + disseminates systematic reviews which shows what is needed in terms of platforms à condenses good and bad evidence in an accessible way for doctors and public			6	JS	20/08/2025 15:05
Consumer network for public which produces lay summaries			7	JS	20/08/2025 15:05
Teach researchers how they can better reach and engage the public			8	JS	20/08/2025 15:19

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
Feedback				9	JS	20/08/2025 15:20
Word of mouth – new participants				10	JS	20/08/2025 15:21
Finding right research questions that matter to the public				11	JS	20/08/2025 15:23
Raw ideas can be powerful if processed				12	JS	20/08/2025 15:24
Stop getting bogged down in narrow pathways				13	JS	20/08/2025 15:24
Codes\\Curiosity & learning						
	No	0.1458	14			
Shared understanding of the research that is being developed				1	JS	20/08/2025 14:31
Curiosity bring people in				2	JS	20/08/2025 14:32
Learning to share your findings to a non-expert audience				3	JS	20/08/2025 14:36
Better understanding of lived experience – this helps guide the research questions asked				4	JS	20/08/2025 14:39
Understanding why fundamental research is important				5	JS	20/08/2025 14:39
Understand how acceptable the things we do in research are to the public				6	JS	20/08/2025 14:40

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				7	JS	20/08/2025 14:40
Understanding how public money is used						
				8	JS	20/08/2025 14:56
Gaining more knowledge about research and how I can use research and outputs						
				9	JS	20/08/2025 14:57
Can ask questions to the specialists						
				10	JS	20/08/2025 15:01
Applying genetic engineering to improve behavioural / cognitive issues						
				11	JS	20/08/2025 15:02
What is biology? What is psychology?						
				12	JS	20/08/2025 15:02
Make information/data more accessible to public/non-expert audience						
				13	JS	20/08/2025 15:03
Meaningful involvement translate in people leaving with something to think of						
				14	JS	20/08/2025 15:24
Make it interesting to the public						
Codes\\Enjoyment & Creativity						
	No	0.0416	4			
				1	JS	20/08/2025 14:39
Hable to have fun in lac and creating						
				2	JS	20/08/2025 14:58
Fun						
				3	JS	20/08/2025 14:58
Creative – more ideas to work on						

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
----------------	-----------	----------	-----------------------------	------------------	-------------------	-------------

Fun			4		JS	20/08/2025 14:59
-----	--	--	---	--	----	------------------

Codes\\Impact

No	0.1666	16
----	--------	----

1	JS	20/08/2025 14:29
Directly involve you in something tat is important for your community		

2	JS	20/08/2025 14:38
Desire to contribute to something good		

3	JS	20/08/2025 14:38
Ensure your research matters to patients		

4	JS	20/08/2025 14:40
Improving public perception of research		

5	JS	20/08/2025 14:52
Contributing to something bigger for the benefit of humanity		

6	JS	20/08/2025 14:52
Rewarding		

7	JS	20/08/2025 14:54
Helping other people / make a difference		

8	JS	20/08/2025 14:57
Public recognition about the project		

9	JS	20/08/2025 15:01
Justify our funding to taxpayers		

10	JS	20/08/2025 15:03
Need to understand your audience in order to target them with the right information		

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
Visibility of what fundamental research is being done + why				11	JS	20/08/2025 15:05
Makes research more representative				12	JS	20/08/2025 15:05
Improves research quality and makes outputs more impactful				13	JS	20/08/2025 15:05
Seeing change / impact				14	JS	20/08/2025 15:20
Use ideas from ordinary public to open new avenues				15	JS	20/08/2025 15:25
Make research attractive to ordinary public				16	JS	20/08/2025 15:29
Codes\\Involvement & engagement						
	No	0.1145	11			
Sharing findings				1	JS	20/08/2025 14:37
Learning to share your findings to a non-expert audience				2	JS	20/08/2025 14:37
Reciprocity				3	JS	20/08/2025 14:55
Engage + empower people to engage with their health				4	JS	20/08/2025 14:59
Meaningful involvement from the public will encourage researchers to carry on involving public in future projects				5	JS	20/08/2025 15:04

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
				6	JS	20/08/2025 15:04
Getting questions from public can be a good sign of meaningful involvement						
				7	JS	20/08/2025 15:06
Funders need to provide research money for engagement activities						
				8	JS	20/08/2025 15:08
Ensure ways of involving people meet individuals accessibility needs so that they don't become barriers -it's involvement + engagement						
				9	JS	20/08/2025 15:21
Repeat engagement						
				10	JS	20/08/2025 15:23
Enriching methods to engage people for young/old people						
				11	JS	20/08/2025 15:24
PI's need to be the people engaging with the public – they are the one writing grants						
Codes\\Personal benefit						
	No	0.0833	8			
				1	JS	20/08/2025 14:54
Access to samples à research progresses						
				2	JS	20/08/2025 14:54
Publications						
				3	JS	20/08/2025 14:55
Financial (initially)						
				4	JS	20/08/2025 14:56
The research benefits you personally						
				5	JS	20/08/2025 14:58
Understanding my health + family health + risks + inheritance						

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
----------------	-----------	----------	-----------------------------	------------------	-------------------	-------------

6 JS 20/08/2025 15:05

Involving public can improve funding perspectives (but this shouldn't be a motivation as a 'tick box' exercise)

7 JS 20/08/2025 15:06

Funders integrate public + patient involvement

8 JS 20/08/2025 15:19

Being able to talk to researcher

Codes\\Representation & Inclusion

No 0.0729 7

1 JS 20/08/2025 14:32

Encourage public members to participate in future research

2 JS 20/08/2025 14:37

Develop understanding to overcome fear in the community and being represented

3 JS 20/08/2025 14:54

Sense of belonging

4 JS 20/08/2025 14:57

Caring about specific community.

5 JS 20/08/2025 14:57

Not targeting the right area. More engagement should be done to find the targeted population

6 JS 20/08/2025 14:58

Bringing researchers' attention to the community that they study – Not much black people in the research project. Can create awareness to the lack of community. It's beneficial from the recruitment point of view (good for EDI)

7 JS 20/08/2025 15:25

Outreach – diversity

Classification	Aggregate	Coverage	Number Of Coding References	Reference Number	Coded By Initials	Modified On
Codes\\Transparency & trust						
	No	0.0937	9			
				1	JS	20/08/2025 14:51
To get public trust						
				2	JS	20/08/2025 14:51
To do research ethically						
				3	JS	20/08/2025 14:50
Informed consent						
				4	JS	20/08/2025 14:55
Visibility						
				5	JS	20/08/2025 15:02
Incentives for researchers to make research transparent /accessible						
				6	JS	20/08/2025 15:02
Information need to be transparent						
				7	JS	20/08/2025 15:06
Increasing public trust is essential						
				8	JS	20/08/2025 15:22
Simplified, condensed but transparent information						
				9	JS	20/08/2025 15:29
Better, more accessible literature						